

Trust Node Identification Scheme for Manet

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Abstract

The work is proposed based upon Direct Trust Calculation was used in which zero while be discarded and one will be selected and which become the best path to send the packet from source to destination. Direct trust calculation also identifies the malicious node The role of malicious is to drop all the data packet and send false route reply. The main role Trust node identification scheme is to identify and remove the attacker's path and select a genuine path to send the data packet to the sender. The Simulation result shows the improvement of better results using performance metrics such as Packet Delivery Ratio, Throughput and End to End delay.

Introduction

An Ad-hoc network is a collection of mobile nodes, which forms a temporary network without the aid of centralized administration or standard support devices regularly available as conventional networks [1]. These nodes generally have a limited transmission range and, so, each node seeks the assistance of its neighboring nodes in forwarding packets and hence the nodes in an Ad-hoc network can act as both routers and hosts. Thus a node may forward packets between other nodes as well as run user applications. By nature these types of networks are suitable for situations where either no fixed infrastructure exists or deploying network is not possible. Ad hoc mobile networks have found many applications in various fields like military, emergency, conferencing and sensor networks. Each of these application areas has their specific requirements for routing protocols. Limitations of MANETs: They provide access to information and services regardless of geographic position.

These networks can be set up at any place and time. Independence from central network administration. Self-configuring network, nodes also act as routers. Self-configuring network, nodes also act as routers. Less expensive as compared to the wired network. Scalable-accommodates the addition of more nodes.Improved Flexibility. Robust due to decentralize administration. The routing protocols for ad hoc wireless networks can be broadly classified into four categories based on Routing information update mechanism, Use of temporal information for routing, Routing Topology, Utilization of specific resources. Classification of routing protocols shows in figure 1.

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Figure 1 Classification of Routing Protocol

Ad hoc wireless network routing protocols can be classified into three major categories based on the routing information update mechanism [2]. They are: Proactive routing protocols are also called table-driven routing protocols. They maintain an absolute picture of the network at every single node in the form of tables. These are good for networks which have less node mobility or where nodes transmit data frequently. DSDV (destination sequenced distance-vector), WRP (wireless routing protocol), CGSR (cluster-head gateway switch routing protocol) and STAR (source-tree adaptive routing protocol) are some examples of table-driven routing protocols.

Reactive routing protocols are on-demand routing protocols. In which nodes do not contain complete information of the network topology, for the reason that it changes constantly. Path finding process and information exchange process execute when any node requires a path to communicate with the target node. Some examples of reactive routing protocols are ABR (Associativity-Based Routing), AODV (Ad Hoc On-Demand Distance-Vector), LAR (Location-Aided Routing), DSR (Dynamic Source Routing) and. For our simulation using the AODV routing protocol.

Trust Node Identification Scheme for Manet

The proposed approach is detecting and eliminating Malicious node in the route is mainly used to improve the trust of the nodes in MANET. The trust value is estimated based on the packet sequence ID.

Source Initialization

Source nodes initialize to send the route request to all intermediate node. The intermediate nodes forward request to the destination node. If the route discovery is successful, the initiating node receives a route reply message listing a sequence of network hops. All the intermediate nodes send for the route request for within the communication range of the other nodes.

Figure 2 Source Node Initialization, The source node is 8, The destination node is 11

Figure 3 Packet sending from source 8 to destination 11 Node 8 sends the packet from destination 11 via the intermediate nodes 45. Node 45 forward the packet from the neighbor node of the destination node. Only the intermediate nodes send the packet from communication range. The packet sends from the way of node 8 - 22 - 4 - 33 - 11

Identifying Malicious Behavior

The arrivals of malicious attacks degrade the network lifetime and disrupt the data delivery. The malicious node causes the packet dropping and incorrect packet forwarding to the nodes in general.

To identify the malicious node following the steps

Input: Attacker behavior

Output: Packet drop

Step 1: Collect the neighbor Node information

Step 2: if Check (sender packet ID=original Packet ID)

Step 3: Calculate the trust rate

Step 4: Else

Step 5: Detect malicious Node

Figure 4 Node 4 Drop all Forward Packets

Figure 5 Detect Malicious Node. It is a Malicious Node 4

Trust Value Calculation based on Direct Observation

Initially, the neighbor node list is constructed for the input node. From, the packet sequence ID of the particular node is extracted.

In this scheme, an observer node can directly estimate the trust value by using the Bayesian framework with the assumption of an observer node overhear the forwarded packets and compared with the original packets to find the malicious behavior.

The observation scheme based on malicious behavior identification leads to less trust in traditional protocols. But, the trust-aware routing protocols implementation in this dissertation computes the trust rate via sequence ID matching assures the secure data transfer between the nodes.

Trust Node = Number of forward packet / Number of received packet

Trust Value Calculation based on Indirect Observation

Current id = 33 Nexthop= 11

Common Neighborid=25

Common Neighborid=3

Common Neighborid=31

Common Neighborid=28

Common Neighborid=44

Common Neighborid=53

Common Neighborid=45

Common Neighborid=42

DT=0.73 for nexthop 11 at node 0 Time 5.096707

DT=0.73 for nexthop 11 at node 0 Time 5.096707

DT=0.85 for nexthop 11 at node 25 Time 5.096707

DT=0.73 for nexthop 11 at node 0 Time 5.096707

DT=0.73 for nexthop 11 at node 0 Time 5.096707

DT=0.61 for nexthop 11 at node 3 Time 5.096707

DT=0.87 for nexthop 11 at node 31 Time 5.096707

DT=0.53 for nexthop 11 at node 28 Time 5.096707

DT=0.62 for nexthop 11 at node 44 Time 5.096707

DT=0.52 for nexthop 11 at node 53 Time 5.096707

DT=0.59 for nexthop 11 at node 45 Time 5.096707

DT=0.76 for nexthop 11 at node 42 Time 5.096707

Common Neighbor Count=12

Current id = 26 Nexthop= 4

Common Neighborid=0

Common Neighborid=15

Common Neighborid=38

Common Neighborid=40

Common Neighborid=22

Common Neighborid=54

Common Neighborid=37

Common Neighborid=21

Common Neighborid=32

Common Neighborid=49

DT=0.00 for nexthop 4 at node 0 Time 12.005857

DT=0.34 for nexthop 4 at node 15 Time 12.005857

DT=0.05 for nexthop 4 at node 38 Time 12.005857

DT=0.14 for nexthop 4 at node 40 Time 12.005857

DT=0.21 for nexthop 4 at node 22 Time 12.005857
 DT=0.40 for nexthop 4 at node 54 Time 12.005857
 DT=0.16 for nexthop 4 at node 37 Time 12.005857
 DT=0.17 for nexthop 4 at node 21 Time 12.005857
 DT=0.14 for nexthop 4 at node 32 Time 12.005857
 DT=0.28 for nexthop 4 at node 49 Time 12.005857
 Common Neighbor Count=10

Figure 6 Data Transfer from Trust Node

The node with high trust value (SN) is selected and added to the routing path. Then, the graph is updated with the remaining nodes. Then, it checks whether the selected node is the destination or not. If the destination node is not equal to the selected node having maximum trust value, then the selected node is considered as the source node. If the destination node is found to be equal to the node with the maximum trust value, then the routing path is determined.

Genuine path : 8-31-24-48-11

Experimental Results and Analysis

Simulation Environment

Network Simulator (NS2) is Discrete Event-Driven simulator developed at UC Berkely. It is part of the VINT project. The goal of ns2 support networking research and education. It is suitable for designing new protocols, comparing different protocols and traffic evaluations. NS2 is developed as collaborative environments it is distributed freely and open source. A large number of institutes and people in development and research use, maintain and develop NS2. Simulation environment consists of 50 wireless mobile nodes which are placed uniformly and forming a mobile ad hoc network, moving about over a 1500x 800 meters area for 100 seconds of simulated time. All mobile node in the network is configured to Source Routing Protocol (AODV).

Table 3 Simulation Parameters

Simulation	Parameters
Routing Protocols	AODV
Simulation Time	100 sec
Area dimension	1000 X 800
Number of nodes	50
Traffic type	CBR
Mobility model	Random Waypoint model
Packet size	404 Bytes

Performance Metrics

To correspond to the special distinctiveness and recital of the network following metrics are used in our simulation:

Throughput

This metric refers to the number of delivered packets in compare with sent packets in the different number of connections.

Throughput may be affected by various factors like transmission medium, the processing power of network components and end-user behavior.

Throughput= $\frac{Pr}{(T2-T1)}$, Where, Pr is total data size received, T1 is the start time and T2 is the stop time of simulation.

Table 1 Throughput

Throughput for Existing Work	Throughput for Existing Work
0.003849	0.003849
0.004658	0.046581
0.00686886	0.0068688

Figure 7 Throughput

Average end-to-end Delay

This metric refers to delay caused by the security mechanism. Also, it can be stated that it refers to packet delivery time. In our study, delay refers to the time between starting security mechanism and delivering data packets to the destination. The reason is that, in some approaches, security mechanism could not detect all malicious nodes in the first performing of the algorithm. Due to MANET’s dynamic topology, time which is spent for each security mechanism is highly challengeable. Link break, due to node’s mobility, is strongly possible in MANET and this need rerouting process for finding the new path.

Delay= (T2-T1)

Where, T2 is received time and T1 is sent time

Table 2 End to End Delay

Existing Work for End to End Delay	Proposed Work for End to End Delay
0.0265569	1.25575
0.041944	0.0332815

Figure 8 End to End delay

Packet Delivery Ratio

PDR is the ratio between the number of packets transmitted by a traffic source and the number of packets received by a traffic sink. It measures the loss rate and characteristics both the correctness and efficiency of MANETs routing protocol. It represents the maximum throughput that the network can achieve. A high PDR is desired in a network.

$$PDR = (Pr/Ps) * 100$$

Where, Pr is total packets received and Ps is the total packets sent

Table 3 Packet Delivery Ratio

Time	Existing Packet Delivery Ratio	Proposed Packet Delivery Ratio
1.0	39	40
2.0	24.1379	25.1379
3.0	26.1905	31.1905

Figure 9 Packer Delivery Ratio

Conclusion and Future Work

A wireless communication system which does not require any fixed infrastructure for the establishment of its configuration is called Mobile Ad hoc Network (MANET). Dynamic topology and hop-by-hop communications of MANET made security in routing protocols highly challengeable. This infrastructure leads to the misbehavior of some nodes which attack and degrade the performance of the network. A malicious node uses the routing protocol's vulnerability and leads all data packets toward itself. In this thesis detection and elimination of malicious nodes in the route discovery mechanism for mobile ad hoc network which uses a direct trust calculation and routes discovery process to detecting and eliminating malicious nodes. The proposed approach achieved high throughput and PDR and optimal end-to-end delay and less false positives.

Future work Our future work will include another security enhancement using location key management protocol. Enhancing the security by using location and key-based security scheme is considered as the future work.

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